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Examining the Influence of Leadership Competencies on Employees' Work Engagement

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study was to investigate the effect of leadership competencies on employees' work engagement. To deepen our understanding of this relationship, relevant literature and theories were reviewed. A descriptive assessment and correlational research design were used, with the population of the study consisting of employees at Divine Word College of Laoag. Validated research questionnaires were used to gather data. The study found that both the leadership competencies of administrators and the work engagement of employees were high, and there was a significant positive correlation between the two. Based on these findings, it is recommended that organizations focus on improving leadership competencies to enhance employees' work engagement.

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Introduction

Successful organizations require more than just managerial skills such as planning, organizing, leading, and controlling. They also need competent leaders who possess the skills to manage the organization and achieve its vision and mission. Individuals in leadership positions must understand their role as both a manager and a leader. It's important to distinguish between the two roles to know when to act as a manager and when to act as a leader. Balancing the two roles can help leaders and managers achieve their organizational goals.

However, both management and leadership can also contribute to organizational failure (Gonfa, 2019). Poor management occurs when an individual lacks skill in planning, organizing, leading, and controlling, while bad leadership arises when there is no vision, motivation, communication, empowerment, and a conducive learning environment (Ellah, 2016; Sydanmaanlakka, 2003). Leadership deficiencies often result in high turnover and job dissatisfaction, which can negatively impact organizational productivity (Gonfa, 2019).

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Previous studies have explored the impact of mismanagement on students' learning. For example, Bloom et al. (2005) found a strong association between higher management quality and better educational outcomes. Similarly, Ross and Gray's (2006) study showed a significant correlation between school leadership and academic achievement. Molina and Wilichowski's (2018) study compared the management practices of manufacturing companies and school principals and found that the former was better at managing their firms. These findings support Tobin's (2014) view that effective school leaders can influence teacher effectiveness and organizational practice.

This study has an educational context and determine the perceived leadership competence of administrators at Divine Word College of Laoag and its effect on employees' work engagement. The study seeks to develop leadership training to help the school achieve excellence in accreditation and quality assurance while considering the relationship between leadership and work engagement. Previous studies have explored the impact of leadership on work performance and work engagement, such as Abun et al. (2017, 2021) who studied the effect of leadership styles on institutional work performance, and Ollan and Roussel (2017) and Cizreliogullari et al. (2017) who investigated the effects of leadership on employee/faculty work engagement. Notably, both studies found a significant correlation between the variables. This study, therefore, focuses on the impact of leadership competencies on work engagement.

The study comprises five distinct parts. The first part is the introduction which sets the context for the study. The second part is the literature review which deepens the understanding of the topic and establishes its theoretical framework. Thirdly, the research methodology provides a detailed description of the methods used to collect and analyze data, ensuring that the study's results are valid and reliable. The fourth part presents the data that were gathered through interviews and analyzed using appropriate statistical techniques to identify patterns, trends, and relationships. The final part is the results and discussion. This explains the implications of the study's findings and their significance in the context of the research objectives. It also highlights the limitations of the study and offers recommendations for future research.

Literature Review

The purpose of the literature review is to deepen the understanding of the study's concept and to establish theories to be investigated. The presentation of the literature review is arranged thematically.

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

The Concept of Leadership and Leadership Styles

Drucker (1996) defines leadership as raising vision and performance, while Bennis (2009) emphasizes knowing oneself, communicating a vision, building trust, and taking effective action. Maxwell (1997) sees leadership as the ability to influence, Kissinger (2022) empowers followers to challenge their limits, and Broadwell and Blanchard (2018) view leaders as servants. Secretan (2004) uniquely sees leadership as inspiration.

Transformational leadership style by Burns (1978) and Bass (1985) involves four components: idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration. It causes a change in the individual

and social system, leading to superior results. The leader serves as a role model, motivates, and inspires followers, encourages creativity and innovation, and coaches or mentors, employee.

Transactional leadership is the opposite of transformational leadership, using a "give and take" approach where rewards are offered for job performance or achieving results. This style relies on structure and obedience to rules and was introduced by Weber (1947), divided into three categories: traditional, charismatic, and legal/bureaucratic. It assumes that employees lack self-motivation and need constant monitoring and instructions to achieve organizational objectives.

Servant leadership, developed by Greenleaf (1977), is like transformational leadership and involves four components: service to others, a holistic approach to work, promoting a sense of community, and sharing power in decision-making. Greenleaf (1996) emphasizes that legitimate and authentic leadership comes from the desire to help others and not exercising power and authority. To achieve organizational objectives, servant leaders should establish a sense of community among their followers and nurture a participatory spirit, empower the environment, and develop the talents of their followers.

The Concept of Leadership Competency

Competency refers to an individual's ability to meet external standards and possesses the necessary knowledge and skills to perform a job or activity (Ahadzie et al., 2008; Cheng et al., 2003; Tett et al., 2000; Trivellas & Drimoussis, 2013; Sampson 1998; Saruchera, 2022; Valyavskiy, et al., 2018; Merriam-Webster, n.d; Cambridge-Dictionary, n.d, and Hoffmann, 1999). It includes the dimensions of behavioral action that support competent performance, with contextual meanings. According to various sources, competency is the possession of sufficient knowledge or skills required to achieve competent performance. It is a prerequisite for improving individual effectiveness and is acquired through education. Overall, competency is essential for successfully executing a job or activity.

Dulewicz and Higgs (2003;2005) identified three competency dimensions: intellectual (IQ), managerial (MQ), and emotional (EQ). Competency can refer to possessing knowledge and skills for adequate performance in substantive domains or specific and generic competencies such as learning ability, communication, and teamwork skills (Thompson et al., 1997). Some prefer integrated frameworks that encompass cognitive, motivational, and social competencies (Bloom, 1956; Boyatzis, 1982; Levy-Leboyer, 1996). This study investigated leadership competency, including vision, achievement-oriented needs, empowerment, teamwork, teaching, change management, and communication (Sydänmaanlakka, 2003). Effective leaders must have a clear vision, the determination to achieve goals, and the ability to manage change (Abun, 2018; Braley, 2021). Change management is considered one of the most critical leadership skills.

The Difference between Management and Leadership

Leadership and management require different skills and functions. Bennis and Nanus (1985) identified leadership as the ability to do the right things, promote networks, and seek commitment to achieve commonly shared outcomes. Meanwhile, Northouse (2000) expanded on this by highlighting the importance of influencing others to achieve these

outcomes. Jarad (2012) listed leadership functions as establishing direction, creating a vision, and building teams, among others. On the other hand, management functions include planning, organizing, executing, allocating resources, and setting attainable objectives, as stated by Emad (2014:118) and Jarad (2012). These functions include establishing order, providing structure, controlling and problem-solving, and generating creative solutions, among others. A successful leader knows when to function as a leader and a manager, using the appropriate skills and functions to achieve the desired outcome.

Numerous studies (Karamat, 2013; Ibrahim & Daniel, 2019; Al-Habib, 2020; Jelinek, 2007; Kinoti, 2012; Paul & Anantharaman, 2020; Anwar et al., 2021) have demonstrated the positive impact of effective leadership and management practices on organizational performance. These findings suggest a correlation between good leadership and management practices. Effective leaders are able to analyze issues critically, focus on long-term goals, and motivate and influence their subordinates to achieve organizational objectives (Zaleznik, 2004).

The Concept of Work Engagement.

Raghavan (2011) highlighted that globally, one-third of employees are not motivated by their work, emphasizing the need for management to shift their focus from merely managing productivity to work engagement. Woodruff (2006) stressed that engaging talented employees should be a top priority. According to the Gallup Report 2021, "highly engaged business units result in 21% greater profitability," and organizations with high employee engagement are more resilient and better equipped to face challenges such as the pandemic, economic collapse, and societal unrest (Harter, 2021). Organizations have a responsibility to cultivate work behavior that motivates employees to improve business performance. Raghavan (2011) also noted that engaged employees are more likely to exhibit positive work behavior, while disengaged employees can lead to negative work behavior. Work engagement, as introduced by Kahn (1990), occurs at three levels: physical, cognitive, and emotional. Schaufeli et al. (2006) defined work engagement as "an active, positive work-related state characterized by vigor, dedication, and absorption." This motivational state drives behavior (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2010). Robinson et al. (2004) defined work engagement as "a positive attitude held by employees toward the organization and its values," suggesting that employees' beliefs about the organization are the source of work engagement. Such beliefs result in a positive attitude toward the organization, motivating employees to improve work performance. Work engagement is not only the concern of the Human Resource manager, but it involves all leader-managers of the organization (Harter, 2021).

Work engagement is a multidimensional construct, meaning that it is measured based on multiple dimensions. Kahn (1990) identified three dimensions: physical, cognitive, and emotional. Schaufeli et al. (2006) encompass three elements, namely vigor, dedication, and absorption. Schaufeli, Salanova, Gonzalez-Roma & Bakker, (2002) measure work engagement on the three dimensions of mental, emotional, and physical engagement. Kuok and Taormina (2017) identified three dimensions to be measured: cognitive, affective (emotional), and conative (physical) work engagement. These three dimensions are interdependent. The focus of this study is to measure the three dimensions of work engagement, namely cognitive, affective (emotional), and conative (physical) dimensions.

Conceptual Framework

Source: Sydänmaanlakka, 2003 and Ellah (2016) Kuok and Taormina (2017).

Figure 1: The conceptual framework explains the relationship between leadership competencies and work engagement. It describes the effect of leadership competency on work engagement.

Statement of the Problems

The study examined the effect of leadership competency on the work engagement of employees. It answered the following questions:

1. What is the leadership competency of administrators in terms of?

- 1.1 vision;*
- 1.2 achievement-oriented need;*
- 1.3 empowerment;*
- 1.4 teamwork;*
- 1.5 teaching;*
- 1.6 change management; and*
- 1.7 communication.*

2. What is the work engagement of employees in terms of?

- 2.1 cognitive engagement;*
- 2.2 affective engagement; and*
- 2.3 conative engagement.*

3. Is there a relationship between leadership competency and the work engagement of employees?

Assumption

The study posits that leadership competency is a crucial factor in effectively leading an organization and has a significant impact on employees' work engagement levels. Furthermore, the study assumes that both leadership competency and work engagement are measurable constructs.

Hypothesis

Based on the studies of Mwithi, et al (2017), and Rohana and Abdullah (2017), leadership competency has a positive significant relationship with the performance of the organization. Hence, the current study hypothesizes that leadership competency affects the work engagement of employees.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study focuses on the relationship between leadership competency and work engagement, specifically examining the dimensions of cognitive, affective, and conative work engagement. Leadership competencies considered in this study include vision, achievement-oriented, empowerment, teamwork, teaching, change management, and communication. The investigation is delimited to the employees and administrators of the Divine Word College of Laoag.

Research Methodology

The quality and reliability of a study depend on the research methodology, which includes the procedures and techniques used to carry out the investigation scientifically (Wilkinson & Birmingham, 2003). In this study, appropriate research methodologies were utilized, such as the research design, data gathering instruments, population, the locale of the study, data gathering procedures, and statistical treatment of data, to ensure the accuracy and validity of the results.

Ethical Consideration

The ethical review of research ethic committee was waived because the study did not involve human subjects.

Research Design

The study adopted a quantitative research approach and utilized a descriptive and correlational research design to assess the level of leadership competency among administrators and its impact on the work engagement of employees. Descriptive research is used to provide a detailed description of the data collected through questionnaires and analyzed using statistical techniques. It is also utilized to describe the characteristics of people, situations, phenomena, or relationship variables. Essentially, descriptive research provides information about "what is" in the data (Ariola, 2006, as cited by Abun, 2019). The current study employed the descriptive assessment and correlational method to determine the level of leadership competency and its effect on work engagement.

Locale of the Study

The locale of the study was Divine Word Colleges of Laoag, Laoag City, Ilocos Norte

Population

The study was conducted with the participation of all employees and faculty members of Divine Word College of Laoag, Ilocos Norte, making up the population of the study. The total number of respondents was 276, using the method of complete enumeration sampling.

Data Gathering Instruments

The researcher secured permission from the Colleges' Presidents to administer the questionnaires to the students. The researcher personally met with the Presidents and students to request their participation. The retrieval of the questionnaires was arranged between the Presidents' representatives and the researcher, with the assistance of college employees and faculty.

Data Gathering Procedures

To collect data, the researcher first obtained permission from the President of the college by sending a letter. Then, the researcher personally distributed and collected the questionnaires from the employees and faculty of the college. The retrieval of the questionnaires was arranged with the help of employees and faculty representatives.

Statistical Treatment of Data

As the study employed a descriptive assessment and correlational research design, descriptive and inferential statistics were utilized. Descriptive statistics, particularly the weighted mean, were used to determine the level of leadership competencies and work engagement. The correlation between leadership competency and work engagement was measured using Pearson's r .

The following ranges of values with their descriptive interpretation will be used:

<i>Statistical Range</i>	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
<i>4.21-5.00</i>	<i>Strongly Agree/Very High</i>
<i>3.41-4.20</i>	<i>Agree/High</i>
<i>2.61-3.40</i>	<i>Somewhat Agree/Moderate</i>
<i>1.81-2.60</i>	<i>Disagree/Low</i>
<i>1.00-1.80</i>	<i>Strongly Disagree/Very Low</i>

Data Presentation and Analysis

This part presents data that were gathered through research questionnaires. The data are presented in the table and follow the statement of the problems.

Problem 1: What is the leadership competency of administrators in terms of?

- 1.1 vision;*
- 1.2 achievement-oriented need;*
- 1.3 empowerment;*
- 1.4 teamwork;*
- 1.5 teaching;*
- 1.6 change management; and*
- 1.7 communication.*

Table 1: Leadership Competency in Terms of Vision

	Vision	Mean	DI
No	Indicators		
1	Has a clear vision and strategy	3.62	A/H
2	Defines a vision of future realities	3.56	A/H
3	Sees the light at the end of the tunnel	3.53	A/H
4	Creates strategic visions (who we are, where we are going, what we can be)	3.59	A/H
5	Establishing short- or long-term objectives, usually incorporating deadlines and assessable factors	3.48	A/H
	Composite mean	3.56	A/H

Source: Sydänmaanlakka, (2003) and Ellah (2016)

Legend:

- 4.21-5.00 *Strongly Agree/Very High*
- 3.41-4.20 *Agree/High*
- 2.61-3.40 *Somewhat Agree/Moderate*
- 1.81-2.60 *Disagree/Low*
- 1.00-1.80 *Strongly Disagree/Very Low*

A competent leader must have a clear vision, as direction is essential for effective leadership. According to the data, the administrators' leadership competency in terms of vision obtained a composite mean of 3.56, which is considered "agree/high." This mean score suggests that the administrators' leadership competency with respect to vision is not very high, nor is it low or moderate, but rather falls on the high end. Each indicator was rated similarly, with all receiving mean scores within the same range, indicating agreement among employees that administrators have a clear vision and strategy (3.62), a definition of future realities (3.56), a view of a better future (3.53), a strategic vision (3.59), and long and short-range objectives (3.48).

Having a vision is a crucial aspect of leadership as it provides a clear direction for an organization to strive towards. A vision serves as a roadmap for leaders to guide their teams toward achieving future goals. According to Kouzes and Posner (1987), great leader envisions an exciting and focused future for their organization. All plans and activities should be aimed at achieving the strategic vision, which should be the main priority for a leader. Hickman and Silva (1984) describe a vision as a mental roadmap toward a better future, serving as an inspiring force that gives meaning to all members of the organization

Table 2: Leadership competency along with achievement-oriented

	Achievement oriented	Mean	DI
No	Indicators:		
1	Commits to the tasks and bring always his/her assignments to the end	3.48	A/H
2	Leads by their example	3.52	A/H
3	Sets clear performance objectives which he/she follows	3.49	A/H
4	Tries to find better, faster, and more efficient ways to do things	3.49	A/H
5	Wants to successfully conclude everything he/she starts	3.58	A/H
	Composite mean	3.51	A/H

Source: Sydänmaanlakka, (2003) and Ellah (2016)

While leadership with a vision is crucial, it becomes meaningless without clear strategies, objectives, and performance indicators to guide actions. As shown in the table data, the administrators' overall leadership competency in achievement orientation received a composite mean rating of 3.51, which is interpreted as "agree/high." This composite mean suggests that the administrators' leadership competency in achievement orientation is not very high, nor is it very low, low, or moderate, but rather falls on the high end. Similarly, each item received mean scores within the same range, indicating agreement among employees that administrators commit to achieving goals (3.48), led by example (3.52), set clear performance objectives (3.49), seek better ways to achieve objectives (3.49), and strive to complete everything they start (3.58).

Achievement-oriented leadership is a critical component of effective leadership as achievement is what defines leadership. Such leadership fosters superior performance and encourages continuous improvement by instilling confidence in followers and inspiring them to follow suit (APA Dictionary of Psychology, n.d.). Setting goals is crucial for leaders as they provide a definition of progress and accomplishments (CEOPedia Management, n.d.).

Table 3: Leadership competency concerning empowerment.

	Empowerment	Mean	DI
No	Indicators:		
1	Ability to delegate challenging tasks according to the abilities of his/her subordinates.	3.51	A/H
2	Motivates his/her subordinates	3.49	A/H
3	Creates a culture in which people can enjoy their work	3.48	A/H
4	Tries to encounter everyone as an individual and take into consideration his/her needs and feelings.	3.57	A/H
5	Trusts people by giving them freedom, power, resources and information	3.54	A/H
	Composite mean	3.52	A/H

Source: Sydänmaanlakka, (2003) and Ellah (2016)

Effective leadership requires more than just the efforts of the leader, as achieving goals is a collaborative effort that involves the people. A leader must create an environment that fosters the willingness of individuals to carry out their duties and responsibilities. Empowerment is a crucial element in creating such an environment. Leadership and empowerment are interconnected as the definition of leadership implies empowerment. According to Helmold and

Samara (2019) and Fatma (2015), leadership involves motivating and directing a group of people to work together to achieve common goals and objectives, which involves formal and informal power distribution.

Based on the data, it is evident that the leadership competency of administrators with respect to the empowerment dimension received a composite mean rating of 3.52, which indicates "agree/high". This mean rating suggests that administrators' leadership competency in empowerment is relatively high, falling within the same level of mean rating when taken individually. Employees agree that administrators delegate tasks to subordinates according to their abilities (3.51), motivate them to perform their duties (3.49), create a culture in which employees enjoy their work (3.48), treat everyone as individuals and consider their needs and feelings (3.57), and trust individuals by providing them with freedom, power, resources, and information (3.54).

Table 4: Leadership competency related to Teamwork

	Teamwork	Mean	DI
No	Indicators:		
1	Ability to lead team operations naturally and efficiently	3.50	A/H
2	Creates and maintains a positive atmosphere in the team	3.46	A/H
3	Recognizes and uses different kinds of competencies of team members	3.54	A/H
4	Makes certain that the team will achieve the objectives set efficiently	3.52	A/H
5	Sets team objectives before his/her objectives	3.52	A/H
	Composite mean	3.51	A/H

Source: Sydänmaanlakka, (2003) and Ellah (2016)

Overall, administrators have a high level of leadership competency in teamwork, with a composite mean of 3.51. Employees agree that administrators effectively lead the team, create a positive atmosphere, utilize the skills of organizational members, and prioritize team goals over personal objectives. Organizational success depends on the ability of leaders to create an environment that fosters effective communication, collaboration, and collective action (Kozlo. To achieve this, leaders should maintain positivity, utilize team members' talents, stimulate positive participation, and promote resilience.

Table 5: Leadership competency in terms of teaching

	Teaching	Mean	DI
No	Indicators:		
1	Helps subordinates when they are encountering work-related problems	3.49	A/H
2	Has regular planning and development discussions with all his/her subordinates	3.42	A/H
3	Gives continuous feedback to subordinates	3.42	A/H
4	Motivates subordinates and gets them to try their best	3.48	A/H
5	Uses his/her time also to develop other managers	3.48	A/H
	Composite mean	3.46	A/H

Source: Sydänmaanlakka, (2003) and Ellah (2016)

Leaders help subordinates solve work problems and develop their skills, as stated by Maxwell (1995), who defines successful leadership as the ability to cultivate other leaders. Overall, the leadership competency of administrators in teaching received a high rating of 3.46, with all indicators rated similarly as "agree/high," according to the data.

Employees agreed that administrators provide support, feedback, and motivation, and prioritize developing other managers.

Table 6: Leadership competency concerning change management

	Change Management	Mean	DI
No	Indicators:		
1	commits to changing the existing problems	3.50	A/H
2	Recognizes and tries to abolish obstacles to change	3.51	A/H
3	Communicates achievements, results and the progress of change	3.50	A/H
4	Always ready for changes and change also himself/herself	3.45	A/H
5	Ability to act flexibly and efficiently in new situations and groups	3.46	A/H
	Composite mean	3.48	A/H

Source: Sydänmaanlakka, (2003) and Ellah (2016)

Leaders bring change to organizations, as noted by Abun (2018), while Bennis (1989) argues that leadership is necessary for survival in a volatile market. According to data on leadership competency, administrators received a high composite mean rating of 3.48 in the change dimension, with all indicators rated similarly as "agree/high." Employees reported that administrators are committed to solving problems, removing obstacles, communicating progress, and adapting to new situations.

Table 7: Leadership competency in terms of communication

	Communication	Mean	DI
No	Indicators:		
1	Speaks openly and directly about performance problems with others	3.54	A/H
2	Listens to suggestions and comments and makes changes if the situation allows it.	3.53	A/H
3	Communicates the organization's values in terms of specific statements on specific issues.	3.49	A/H
4	Communicates to explore issues and develop solutions	3.48	A/H
5	Expresses oneself effectively both orally and in written form	3.55	A/H
	Composite mean	3.52	A/H
	Overall Mean	3.50	A/H

Source: Sydänmaanlakka, (2003) and Ellah (2016)

Effective communication is a crucial leadership competency as it fosters trust, alignment, and positive change (Gallo, 2022; Landry, 2019). The data shows that the leadership competency of Divine Word College of Laoag's administrators in communication is rated as "agree/high" with a mean rating of 3.50. This suggests that while their overall leadership competency is not low or moderate, there is still room for improvement. The employees acknowledge that administrators communicate openly and clearly about performance (3.54) and effectively express themselves (3.55). The overall leadership competency mean rating is 3.50, with all dimensions rated similarly: vision (3.56), achievement-oriented (3.51), empowerment (3.52), teamwork (3.51), teaching (3.46), change management (3.48), and communication (3.50).

Problem 2: What is the work engagement of employees in terms of?

2.1 Cognitive engagement

2.2 Affective engagement

2.3 Conative engagement

Table 8: Work engagement in terms of Cognitive engagement

	Cognitive engagement	Mean	DI
No	Indicators:		
1	My mind is often full of ideas about my work	3.48	A/H
2	Wherever I am, things happen that often remind me of my work.	3.40	SWA
3	My mind is fully engaged with my work	3.35	SWA
4	I rarely think about a time when I am working	3.44	A/H
5	My thoughts are fully focused when thinking about my work	3.39	SWA
6	I give a lot of mental attention to my work.	3.36	SWA
	Composite Mean	3.40	SWA

Source: Kuok and Taormina (2017)

Work engagement's cognitive factor is a predictor of organizational success. Employees with a positive attitude toward their work and a clear understanding of their tasks are more engaged, leading to better performance. Collaboration between employees and employers is crucial in problem-solving (Fachrunnisa, et al., 2022). The data shows that the overall cognitive engagement of employees has a moderate mean rating of 3.40. Most items were rated as "somewhat agree/moderate," indicating that employees generally give mental attention to their work, focus their thoughts on their work, and have their minds engaged in their work. Only two items were rated as "high," such as having their minds full of ideas about their work and rarely thinking about the time while working.

Table 9: Work engagement concerning affective engagement.

	Affective Engagement	Mean	DI
No	Indicators		
1	I feel very delighted about what I am doing whenever I am working.	3.41	A/H
2	I am very eager to do my work	3.39	SWA
3	I feel very happy when I am carrying out my responsibilities at work.	3.42	A/H
4	I feel very good about the work that I do.	3.56	A/H
5	I feel strong enthusiasm for my work.	3.58	A/H
6	I feel a sense of gratification from my work performance	3.64	A/H
	Composite mean	3.50	A/H

Source: Kuok and Taormina (2017)

Affective engagement is another aspect of work engagement that is crucial for achieving high performance, along with cognitive engagement. It is also considered a predictor of organizational performance, as employees who have positive emotions toward their work tend to perform better (Amsi et al., 2022). According to Rothbard (2001) and Sonnentag (2003), employees who feel happy and emotionally attached to their work tend to exhibit better performance. The employees in this study also demonstrated a high level of affective engagement, with a composite mean of 3.50, which is considered "agree/high". This suggests that their work engagement in terms of affective

engagement is high, as supported by the individual items that are rated within the same range with the interpretation of "agree/high". The employees feel delighted (3.41), happy (3.42), good (3.56), enthusiastic (3.64), and a sense of significance (3.64) towards their work performance.

Table 10: Work engagement related to physical engagement.

	Physical engagement (conative)	Mean	DI
No	Indicators:		
1	No matter how much I work, I have a high level of energy	3.64	A/H
2	I have a great deal of stamina for my work.	3.63	A/H
3	I always have a lot of energy for my work	3.65	A/H
4	I am often physically driven by my work	3.62	A/H
5	I am frequently energized by my work.	3.63	A/H
6	I find my work to be physically invigorating	3.64	A/H
	Composite mean	3.63	A/H
	Overall Mean (Cognitive, Affective, and Conative)	3.63	A/H

Source: Kuok and Taormina (2017)

The third dimension of work engagement is physical work engagement, which is necessary for achieving organizational objectives. Nyikuli et al. (2018) found that physical work engagement has a significant correlation with organizational performance. Physical engagement refers to the level of physical effort shown by employees in their job tasks (Khan, 1990). Work engagement requires not only cognitive and affective engagement, but also physical engagement. The composite mean for physical work engagement was 3.63, which is considered "agree/high". This suggests that the physical work engagement of employees is high. Even when the items are considered separately, all are rated within the same range of "agree/high". Employees agreed that they have the necessary energy, stamina, and drive to perform their job tasks and find their work physically invigorating. Overall, the employees' work engagement had a mean rating of 3.63, indicating a high level of agreement. However, when considering the dimensions individually, the cognitive engagement of employees was found to be low.

Problem 3: Is there a relationship between leadership competency and the work engagement of employees?

Table 11: Administrators’ Leadership Competencies & Cognitive Engagement of Employees

The study found that the leadership competencies of DWCL administrators, including vision, achievement-oriented needs, empowerment, teamwork, teaching, change management, and communication, significantly predicted employees' cognitive engagement. The analysis showed that the predictors overlapped by 79.1%, indicating a strong relationship. Specifically, the regression equation revealed that the administrators' leadership competencies in vision, teamwork, and communication significantly influenced employees' cognitive engagement. The Y-intercept for the regression equation was quantified at -.339 for vision, .650 for teamwork, and .465 for communication, indicating their individual impact on cognitive engagement. Therefore, the study concluded that the combined effect of these leadership competencies could predict employees' cognitive engagement, but individually, only vision, teamwork, and communication were significant predictors.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.791a	.626	.609	.59950

a. Predictors: (Constant), Communication, Vision, Teaching, Teamwork, Achievement-Oriented Need, Empowerment, Change Management

ANOVAa

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	91.353	7	13.050	36.311	.000b
	Residual	54.629	152	.359		
	Total	145.983	159			

a. Dependent Variable: Cognitive Engagement

b. Predictors: (Constant), Communication, Vision, Teaching, Teamwork, Achievement-Oriented Need, Empowerment, Change Management

Coefficientsa

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.424	.199		2.135	.034
	Vision	-.339	.169	-.356	-1.999	.047
	Achievement-Oriented Need	.180	.177	.192	1.021	.309
	Empowerment	.066	.193	.063	.343	.732
	Teamwork	.650	.175	.607	3.706	.000
	Teaching	.182	.164	.174	1.113	.268
	Change Management	-.353	.231	-.332	-1.528	.129
	Communication	.465	.222	.435	2.100	.037

a. Dependent Variable: Cognitive Engagement

Table 12: Administrators' Leadership Competencies & Affective Engagement of Employees

When considering the seven leadership competencies of the DWCL administrators, including vision, achievement-oriented need, empowerment, teamwork, teaching, change management, and communication, a significant prediction of employees' affective engagement was observed when all competencies were taken together ($F(7,160) = 30.475$, $p < .01$), with a .764 overlap between the competencies and affective engagement. The regression equation for affective engagement was quantified by the Y-intercept of .609 and a significant effect of the teamwork competency ($B = .433$, $p < .05$). Therefore, the combined leadership competencies of the administrators were able to predict the employees' affective engagement, whereas only the teamwork competency was significant when considered individually.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.764a	.584	.565	.63078

a. Predictors: (Constant), Communication, Vision , Teaching, Teamwork, Achievement-Oriented Need, Empowerment, Change Management

ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	84.877	7	12.125	30.475	.000b
	Residual	60.478	152	.398		
	Total	145.355	159			

a. Dependent Variable: Affective (Emotional) Engagement

b. Predictors: (Constant), Communication, Vision, Teaching, Teamwork, Achievement-Oriented Need, Empowerment, Change Management

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.609	.209		2.917	.004
	Vision	-.266	.178	-.280	-1.491	.138

Achievement-Oriented Need	.200	.186	.214	1.076	.283
Empowerment	.182	.203	.174	.897	.371
Teamwork	.433	.184	.405	2.347	.020
Teaching	.125	.172	.119	.725	.470
Change Management	-.229	.243	-.216	-.945	.346
Communication	.381	.233	.357	1.635	.104

a. Dependent Variable: Affective (Emotional) Engagement

Table 13: Administrators’ Leadership Competencies & Conative (Physical) Engagement of Employees

The results of the regression analysis show that when the leadership competencies of DWCL employees in terms of vision, achievement-oriented need, empowerment, teamwork, teaching, change management, and communication are taken together, they significantly predict the employees' conative engagement. The analysis revealed an overlap of .780 between the different leadership competencies and employees' conative engagement, with $F(7,160) = 33.655$ $p < .01$

Teamwork had the highest impact on conative engagement with a B coefficient of .681 $p < .01$, followed by change management with a B coefficient of -.692 $p < .01$, and communication with a B coefficient of .598 $p < .05$, with a Y-intercept of .658 for the regression equation.

Therefore, the study concludes that when all the leadership competencies of administrators are considered, they can significantly predict the employees' conative engagement. However, when analyzed separately, only teamwork, change management, and communication emerged as significant predictors of the employees' conative engagement.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.780a	.608	.590	.63062

a. Predictors: (Constant), Communication, Vision, Teaching, Teamwork, Achievement-Oriented Need, Empowerment, Change Management

ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	93.690	7	13.384	33.655	.000b
	Residual	60.448	152	.398		

Total	154.139	159			
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a. Dependent Variable: Conative (Physical Engagement)

b. Predictors: (Constant), Communication, Vision, Teaching, Teamwork, Achievement-Oriented Need, Empowerment, Change Management

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.658	.209		3.150	.002
Vision	-.116	.178	-.119	-.651	.516
Achievement-Oriented Need	.191	.186	.198	1.029	.305
Empowerment	-.140	.203	-.130	-.689	.492
Teamwork	.681	.184	.619	3.695	.000
Teaching	.326	.172	.303	1.893	.060
Change Management	-.692	.243	-.634	-2.853	.005
Communication	.598	.233	.543	2.563	.011

a. Dependent Variable: Conative (Physical Engagement)

Results and Discussions

The study investigated the impact of leadership competencies on employee work engagement, finding a significant relationship between the two. The study's results suggest that organizations can enhance employee work engagement by improving their leaders' competencies. Competencies like vision, achievement orientation, empowerment, teamwork, teaching, change management, and communication should be considered when selecting and assigning individuals to leadership positions Brownell, (2006; (Kramer, 2005; (Pelit, et. al. 2011, Hanaysha & Tahir, 2016, Yimam, 2022). Recent research also highlights the importance of new leadership competencies such as high ethical standards, providing direction, clearly communicating expectations, flexibility, ongoing training, open communication, receptivity to new ideas, fostering a sense of shared success and failure, nurturing next-generation leaders, and promoting trial and error (Giles, 2016).

To enhance work engagement, administrators need training and development in vision, achievement orientation, empowerment, teamwork, teaching, change management, and communication (Maran, et al., (2021) (Sijbom, et al.,2016, Okeke, et al. (2019). Moreover, Enyioko(2021); Musheke and Phiri (2021); Xu & Xue (2018) claimed that

effective communication between leaders and subordinates can impact motivation and performance, and a relatable vision can improve employee engagement (Slaten, et al., 2021). Empowerment, teamwork, teaching, and change management also positively affect job satisfaction and performance. The study's findings align with previous research demonstrating the impact of leadership competencies on individual and organizational performance (Rohana & Abdullah, 2017, Asree, et al., 2010, Rahmat, et al., 2021, Rose, et al., 2019, Gul, et al., 2022). Therefore, organizations should focus on developing the competencies of their leaders to enhance employee work engagement and performance.

Conclusion

The study found high leadership competencies among administrators and high work engagement among employees, with a significant correlation between the two. The study recommends increasing positive development in leadership competencies through training and development to improve work engagement. The study contributes to the discussion on leadership competencies in improving organizational performance but recognizes limitations in its scope and population. Future research should broaden the investigation to include a larger population and other institutions, and include more variables related to leadership competencies.

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